

ANALYSIS OF THE CAROTID ARTERY AND ATHEROSCLEROTIC PLAQUE GROWTH USING THE PATIENT-SPECIFIC PARAMETERS

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The main aim of this study was to computationally model the biological and mechanical processes related to the plaque initiation and progression, as well as to predict plaque regions and mechanisms which are prone to atherosclerosis development. The created multiscale model included the patient-specific parameters needed for the 3D geometrical reconstruction of carotid artery and its biological characterisation, in order to computationally simulate the plaque growth.

The patient-specific plaque characterization and 3D carotid reconstruction are based on the medical imaging techniques (using MRI, US, CT), which are performed for creation of refined models and detailed analysis. The 3D blood flow was governed by the Navier-Stokes equations and continuity equation. Mass transfer within the blood lumen and through the arterial wall was coupled with the blood flow and modelled by the convection–diffusion equations, while Kedem-Katchalsky equations described the Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) transport in the arterial lumen. Appropriate boundary conditions were prescribed.

The shear stress distribution and the blood flow characteristics along the carotid artery were analysed at the plaque initiation and follow-up time steps. Analysing the shear stress distribution at the baseline, the zone of a low shear stress indicated the greatest risk of plaque progression, which was confirmed after the follow-up. Atherosclerosis development led to an increase in plaque volume and a decrease in lumen diameter, which was followed by reduced blood flow through the stenotic zone and higher shear stress.

Recent advances in both computational fluid dynamics and imaging techniques have contributed to the modelling of atherosclerotic plaque formation and progression. This approach will be further improved and used for risk stratification models, by detecting the parameters of unstable and stable carotid plaques related to the risk of stroke, which is objective of our future studies.

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